

ASSESSMENT OF STEREOACUITY BEFORE AND AFTER TRANS EPITHELIAL PHOTOREFRACTIVE KERATECTOMY IN MYOPES

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Abstract

Purpose: To evaluate effects of Transepithelial photorefractive keratectomy (Trans-PRK) on stereopsis among the individuals having myopic refractive error.

Methods: 30 individuals were recruited through nonprobability convenient sampling technique in duration from September 2018 to May 2019 from Madina Teaching Hospital. This analytical study included patients undergoing PRK to achieve emmetropia. Best corrected visual acuity was obtained using Snellen vision chart followed by torch light examination. Preliminary examination was done on slit lamp to rule out any corneal pathology that may affect results of study. For stereoacuity TNO test was used on all individuals undergoing trans-PRK. After 2 months of post PRK, same protocol was revised to measure stereopsis. SPSS version 20 was used for statistical analysis.

Results: Significant results were seen among them with the p value of 0.01 at the level of 5% of confidence interval. It was seen that stereoacuity got improved after Trans-PRK when the measurements of stereoacuity were compared before and after the surgery. Refractive error ranging in between 4.00 to 10.50 DS. Mean of refractive error was 6.59. It was seen that in high refractive errors, more compromised stereoacuity values were obtained. Mean of stereoacuity before surgery was 2.47 ± 1.167 and mean of stereoacuity after surgery was 5.40 ± 0.724 .

Conclusion: Trans-PRK can correct myopic error resulting in improvement of stereoacuity as well. As there is high refractive error, functional vision including stereoacuity also got compromised. But after refractive surgery, stereoacuity improved. Trans-PRK is a safe and recommendable method that cures the refractive error and stereoacuity improvement is seen.

INTRODUCTION

Refractive surgery allows refractive errors to be corrected permanently in a safe, effective, and reliable way with minimal complications. Ophthalmic surgeons now have a multiplicity of refractive surgical methods at their disposal for the individualized

correction of refractive errors. Techniques of refractive surgery on the cornea and lens are now available that reliably fulfill the standard criteria of safety, efficacy, cost-effectiveness, and predictability of the refractive outcome. It is an alternative to getting

rid of optical corrections like spectacles or contact lenses. With the passage of time, these procedures are getting better with new technologies.

The surface treatment techniques include photorefractive keratectomy (PRK), laser-subepithelial keratomileusis (LASEK), and epi-LASIK. After Radial Keratotomy (RK), Laser Assisted in Situ Keratomileusis (LASIK) technique was invented by which most of refractive errors were corrected¹.

There is several Laser procedures commonly used now a days for refractive error correction. Laser *in situ* keratomileusis (LASIK) and PRK were the refractive procedures that were being used. Both are valid and reliable procedures through which refractive errors can be corrected (bot spherical and cylindrical component)².

Trans-PRK can correct minimum to high myopia with more efficacy. 6 months after Trans-PRK vision improvement can be seen in all myopic groups including low, moderate and high. Trans-PRK is more demanding now days for the correction of myopic groups i.e. low, moderate, high. Trans-PRK possesses several distinctive features than ordinary PRK. Single ablation is required for removal of epithelium of cornea & stroma in one step. No flap is required in this procedure, so complications related to flaps are also overcome. Negligible amount of trauma can occur³.

In the development of Trans-PRK key factor kept in mind was tidy edge of epithelial wound. Instruments do not meet the eye along with no use of alcohol on cornea. Neglectable number of epithelial defects were needed for abrasion of stroma. Trans-PRK gives rapid healing of epithelium because of zone of ablation of epithelium. Good prognosis of single step Trans-PRK has been seen in low, medium and high refractive errors⁴.

Vision quality was seeing improved along with correction of astigmatism and myopia refractive error through refractive surgery. Myopia does not return after Trans-PRK and recovery is also good. Trans-PRK is a relatively new procedure, and a limited number of publications are currently available. Also, it is helpful for patients who are highly anxious or have a particular phobia about flap creation⁵.

The process of stereopsis aims to perceive three dimensional shapes of objects along with depth perception as both eyes perceive a slightly different

view. As the age of person increases stereopsis also get affected⁶.

Perception of depth is visual ability to come to realize the three dimensions. Through this ability one knows that how far or near this object is placed form the individual and its size can be detected. Impression of depth is created in such a way⁷.

Before and after the Trans-PRK it was seen that refractive error was corrected along with improvement in stereoacuity along with binocular vision as seen previously⁸.

Stereoacuity was also determined before and after LASIK. It was seen that distance and near stereoacuity show improvement after procedure⁹.

Stereoscopic vision is one of the most outstanding characteristics of the human optical system; based on differences in the horizontal position can make accurate decisions about the depth perception, it can take only a few seconds. Stereoscopic vision is three-dimensional vision produced by the fusion of two slightly different views of a scene on each retina. It was clear that stereoscopic vision is worthy to be one of the most impressive and we can say it the hyper acuities¹⁰.

Methodology:

Analytical study was conducted in the Department of Ophthalmology at Madina Teaching Hospital Faisalabad on 30 individuals of both genders with ages ranging from 20 - 35 years. This study was conducted from September 2018 to May 2019. Informed consent was received from all the individuals. TNO test was performed after taking complete ocular, medical, surgical and drug history. Subjects with no systemic or ocular disorders or stable refractive error were included in the study. Subjects with any ocular pathology or history of any ocular surgery, strabismus and amblyopia were excluded from the study. Nonprobability convenient sampling technique was used. After acquiring detail history and examination of anterior and posterior segment, visual status of individuals undergoing Trans-PRK was noted using LCD snellen vision chart followed by retinoscopy. 30 healthy myopic volunteers of 20-35 age groups were taken from ophthalmology department of Madina teaching hospital. Retinoscopic refraction along with subjective refraction was taken. Stereoacuity was assessed on TNO test was repeated with best refractive

correction. After 2 months of Trans-PRK vision assessment along with TNO test. Results were noted down and compared from each subject and expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Results were analyzed on SPSS 20 and were expressed in terms of mean ± standard deviation. Paired t test was applied to establish comparison.

Results:

In this study 30 subjects were included out of which 18 were females and 12 were males with age ranging from 20 to 35 (mean 25.73) years and having refractive error greater than 4.00 DS. Based on refractive error, which was myopia, it was assessed that all 30 patients preoperatively and post operatively. Stereopsis was tested preoperatively and post

operatively. Results were analyzed by paired sample t test.

Mean of stereoacuity of 30 patients before surgery was 2.47 ± 1.167 and mean of stereoacuity after surgery was 5.40 ± 0.724 . It means that stereopsis improves after surgery significantly.

Results are highly significant because stereo-acuity improved after surgery when it was compared with the pre-operative results. And probability value was less than 0.005 ($p < 0.005$) so results are significant according to this. Paired sample t test mean of stereopsis preoperatively and post operatively - 2.933 ± 0.868 . Significant value for paired t test was 0.00. All myopic groups got benefit. Stereopsis improved after Trans-PRK surgery.

Figure no. 1: Age Distribution

This bar graph shows that age group frequency. There were three age groups. Mostly patients were 20 to 25 aged.

Figure no. 2: Comparison of Stereo-acuity before & after Trans PRK

Improvement in stereo-acuity was observed before and after the surgery. Mean of stereoacuity of 30 patients before surgery was 2.47 ± 1.167 and mean of stereo acuity after surgery was 5.40 ± 0.724 . Paired sample t test shows a significant difference between pre-operative and post-operative stereopsis among myopic individuals ($p=0.01$) at the level of 5% of confidence interval.

Discussion

Stereoacuity is considered very important functional vision quality. The present study showed the effect of stereoacuity before and after Trans-PRK surgery among myopes. Stereoacuity was measured with TNO stereoacuity test. Results were recorded on the Performa designed previously. Scoring test plates were made as the response of the individuals. My sample size was 30 patients that had myopia greater than 4.00 DS. Sampling technique was nonprobability convenient sampling. Paired t-test was used for statistical analysis. Stereoacuity was determined binocularly as stereopsis is a binocular procedure. The results of variable; in paired t test showing when there was high refractive error, stereoacuity use to decrease and after Trans-PRK (refractive surgery)

procedure, stereoacuity got improved. 20 – 35-year age group was considered. It was seen that results are highly significant with the p value 0.01.

Research was conducted in school aged children for the purpose that better stereoacuity was required in scene of performance at school. 170 subjects were taken who participated in the study. Stereoacuity was performed using Randot test and changes are seen. Those who have good stereoacuity have been seen performing well¹¹.

In a hospital of Iran 180 people were observed. 3 groups were made including low, moderate and high refractive error for testing stereopsis. Forty patients (80 eyes) had a mean (\pm SD) pre-LASIK refractive error of $-4.70 (\pm 1.72)$ DS OD and $-4.59 (\pm 1.58)$ DS OS and a mean (\pm SD) anisometropia of $0.55 (\pm 0.51)$ DS Most benefitted were people having high myopia¹².

A study was done to assess stereoacuity following wave-front guided PRK in the individuals having anisometropia. Study included 49 patients and 98 eyes were assessed. It was seen that improvement in stereoacuity was seen following wave front guided PRK that were used for anisometropic myopia. TNO and butterfly test was used to check stereoacuity⁸.

A study had been carried out on myopes, and refractive procedure was Trans PRK. In this study 96 myopic eyes were taken. All were examined carefully. Persons who had high refractive error also showed appreciable results³.

In a study that was performed in 2018 Trans PRK for myopic correction. 792 eyes were being assessed. Both procedures were compared, and it was concluded that two of them are excellent in all terms¹³.

Results of this study are like previous study results that were like those of other refractive procedures i.e. RK, LASIK, LASEK. Stereoacuity got improved after Trans-PRK. Similar studies were conducted but not exactly on this topic, but all of these are like my study. Stereoacuity was also observed before and after Trans-PRK refractive surgery and it was found that significant relationship was seen with refractive error. After the refractive surgery, stereoacuity improved as refractive error was cured in the present study. Moreover, previous literature also showed similar results as mentioned earlier.

Conclusion:

It was concluded that stereoacuity got improved significantly after the Trans-PRK. Trans-PRK was considered safe and reliable method to correct the different grades of myopia.

Stereoacuity must be considered during routine examinations. Stereoacuity assessment after Trans-PRK is also essential because this is important component of visual function and necessary for daily vision task like driving. All protocols are done through laser and no touch is required. So, there is not any chance of contamination. There is a high success rate. This surgery is proven to be corrected, and post-surgical enhancements can further improve vision. Future studies must evaluate stereoacuity among different grades of myopia.

No. of figures: 2

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